

UNSKILLED MIGRANT WORKERS

A Christian Ethical Challenge to the Economic Point of View

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Abstract

This paper is an attempt to put into contestation the point of view of economics and that of Christian ethics on the issue of migration, with particular attention to unskilled migrant workers. Economically, the material benefit of the migrant worker business surpasses the moral and legal problems affecting a minority group of unskilled migrant workers. Christian ethics, however, challenges the economic calculation using more fundamental factors as starting points, namely the concept of human worth and the problem of individualizing human being.

Keywords: migrant worker, Christian economic ethics, Christian anthropology, economic anthropology.

INTRODUCTION

During September 2016, I served as interim pastor of the Indonesian community at St Andrew's Presbyterian Church, Kuala Lumpur, as part of my "Service for Community" program. The community's membership covers a broad spectrum of Indonesians who make a living in Kuala Lumpur, including engineers, lecturers, businesspeople, embassy staff, students, and domestic workers. One of the community's programs is doing ministry with migrant workers who are accommodated temporarily in a shelter belonging to the Indonesian embassy. Most of the migrant workers living in that shelter are uneducated women, many are even illiterate, coming from remote areas of Indonesia. They were recruited by "agents" who introduce them to their hosts. The problems being faced by those migrant workers are basically exploitation, sexual abuse, and fraud by the hosts or the agents making use of their lack of knowledge and foreign status.

Unskilled migrant workers from countries like Indonesia and the Philippines are acknowledged to be significant contributors of their countries of origin's national income. With their regular remittance, they certainly improve their families' standard of living. The World Bank data shows that migrant workers' official remittance to their countries of origin reached the amount of US\$401 billion in 2012.¹ It may be true that most migrant workers raise no complaint about their job or their host. Those living in the shelter may not represent the majority of unskilled migrant workers in term of the problem they are facing. Hence, from the economic point of few,

¹ See: Gemma T.Cruz, *Toward a Theology of Migration: Social Justice and Religious Experience*, New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2014, p.21

migrant workers including unskilled ones are part of the advantages of the contemporary transnational market. Christian ethics, however, does not take the sense of the majority as the standard norm. The priority in Christian ethics is given to the needy regardless of their number. Jesus' parable of the lost sheep (Matt 18:12-14) reflects the way Christian ethics puts its priority. It is the lostness, not the number, which matters. Also, one of the tasks of Christian ethics is to question and challenge what is looked normal or even claimed to be good according to another perspective. In this case, Christian ethics does not take for granted the economic point of view. It puts such a point of view into a contestation with the Christian resources notably the Bible. In fact, the issues of the migrant and migration are nothing new to the Bible. As Cruz has noted "The Bible itself is basically 'a literary tapestry woven from the stories of migrants'"²

To be sure, the Bible does not put forth a comprehensive plan for conducting national or international activity. The Bible does have some prescriptions for the way the ancient Hebrew community was to conduct its economic practices, given the time and circumstances in which they lived. Because we live in a different time and place, we will be looking less at these specific economic prescriptions, and more at some ethical inspiration about the way we should treat one another and their application to economics. The major assumptions of Bruce C. Birch and Larry L. Rasmussen in their well known book about the *Bible and Ethics and the Christian Life* hold as the two major presuppositions of the book that first, "Christian ethics is not synonymous with biblical ethics."³ Thus we cannot just apply the Bible

² Ibid, p. 23

³ Bruce C. Birch and Larry L. Rasmussen, *Bible and Ethics in the Christian Life*, Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 1989, p. 11.

in a rote or literal fashion to modern economic problems. However, the second major presupposition of the book is: “The Bible is somehow formative and normative for Christian ethics.”⁴

At the same time, economics does not seem to offer us an ethical code. In fact, most economists would probably say that economics is a way to allocate scarce resources or a way to order preferences, not an ethical code. Economics was not always this way. The germinal book of economics, *The Wealth of Nations* (1776), was written by a moral philosopher, Adam Smith. Smith is also known for other moral philosophy works, including *A Theory of Moral Sentiments*. There has been a long lively debate as to the continuities (or lack thereof) between the two books. It seems that Smith could not get away from his moral training as evidenced by parts of *The Wealth of Nations* on the restraints needed on predatory competition, the interest of society and the public good, and criticisms of the British mercantile system. However, John Maynard Keynes wrote perceptively in the 1920s and 1930s “of how religious values and influences were dropped generally from economic analysis and writing in the latter half of the nineteenth century.”⁵ If the economics we have today does not offer us an ethical code, how can we compare it to a biblical ethical inspiration? I believe that we can derive or abstract certain ethical principles out of current empirical economic behavior in order to make them contestable to Christian ethical premises. The major source for economic thought that I will use in this study is Paul Samuelson and Richard Norhaus’ classic textbook *Economics*.

⁴ Ibid., p. 14.

⁵ Arnold F. McFee, *Economics and the Christian Mind*, New York: Vantage Press, 1987, p. 124.

I want to begin by speaking of the positive side of economics and its accomplishments. In singing the praises of economics, Daly and Cobb tell us, “During the past two centuries, the economy has transformed the character of the planet and especially of human life. It has done so chiefly by industrialization.”⁶ During this period, although populations in the developed world have markedly increased, productivity per worker and the amount of good and services available per person have increased even faster. The standard of living in the developed world has gone from an almost subsistence level to the highest in the world. The discipline of economics has undoubtedly had a strong influence on this growth. Cobb and Daly claim that “public policy has been deeply affected by the ideas and proposals of economists.”⁷ Economics, to some degree, does not try to live in an idealized world, but is realistic, and tries to harness and utilize the way people are, self-interested, not the way we hope them to be, altruistic.

I believe economics has a compelling case, which many people believe, but Christian ethics goes further by asking to whom has all this growth benefited and why? Is God calling humans to be and to become just as in the vision that economics imparts?

Referring to Catholic Social Teaching, Cruz suggests that “the human cost and the tragic nature of contemporary migration obviously brings up questions on human dignity.”⁸ With respect for the unskilled migrant workers’ case, therefore, at least two issues are crucial to examine: the concept of human worth and the problem of individualizing humans.

⁶ Herman E. Daly and John B. Cobb, *For the Common Good: Redirecting the Economy toward Community, the Environment, and Sustainable Future*. Boston: Beacon Press, 1989, p. 3.

⁷ *Ibid.*

⁸ Cruz, p. 57

THE CONCEPT OF HUMAN WORTH

Our first point of contestation between economics and Christianity is on the subject of human worth. What kind of worth do human beings have, extrinsic or intrinsic, and from where do they draw value? The economic and financial realms of the modern world seem to be dominated by what has been called the Machine master image. James Loder defines a master image as “the shared imaginative construction of the world that shapes our lives at the level of corporate, pre-conscious awareness.”⁹ In other words, it is a presupposition that implies a whole core system of values that we may never question or articulate. The master image is usually learned through various socialization processes, and it can exert a powerful influence over the way we shape, conduct, and live our lives. Loder, pulling from Gibson Winter, claims that one of the master images dominating the achievement-oriented, capitalistic society is the image of the Machine. This image says your worth is determined not by who you are, but by what or how much you produce. Loder continues and says: “The achievement-oriented, A-type personality is under the power of the Machine image to get the most done in the shortest amount of time possible. Efficiency is of the essence. If it is faster it is better.” Economics perpetuates, and maybe in some ways has created, this master image. Human beings become variables in equations or economic analyses. In the rush to quantify everything so the economist can analyze it, economics has quantified people into what or how much they can produce, or how much money they can make. Thus, according to the discipline of economics, our worth as human beings is extrinsic. We are no longer worthwhile for who we are, but for the value and

⁹ James Loder, *Culture: The Word and Cultural Transformation*. unpublished paper, Princeton Theological Seminary, 3/28/95, p. 3.

quantity of what we produce. This is one anthropological assumption that underlies the discipline of economics.

Christian ethics works under a very different rubric for its conception of the worth of human beings. First, I believe that a presupposition of Christian ethics is that human beings have not extrinsic worth as a commodity or factor of production, but intrinsic worth. “Christianity is the source of the conviction that every person has an absolute value,” as Diogenes Allen claims.¹⁰ Why does every human being have such precious value? Every human being is created in the image of God. We see an example of this in the first creation account in Genesis which reads: “So God created humankind in his image, in the image of God he created them; male and female he created them” (Genesis 1:27). There is much debate over exactly what the image of God in human beings does or does not entail. John Calvin alludes to this verse in speaking of our “primal worthiness.”¹¹ Whatever it is that constitutes the image of God in human beings, Calvin claims that being created in God’s image denotes our “participation in God.”¹² In his exegetical analysis of this verse, Gordon J. Wenham says: “The image of God means that in some sense that men and women resemble God and the angels, though where the resemblance lies is left undefined in this chapter.”¹³ I feel that to resemble the Omniscient, Almighty Creator is a very important axiom for anthropology. Roelf L. Haan, in an article contrasting Christianity and economics claims:

¹⁰ Diogenes Allen, *Love: Christian Romance, Marriage, Friendship*. Eugene: Wipf & Stock, 2006, p. 20.

¹¹ John Calvin, *Institutes of the Christian Religion*, ed. 1536, vol. 2, 1, 1, Grand Rapids: Wm B. Eerdmans, 1995, p. 242.

¹² *Ibid.*, vol. 2, 2, 1, p. 470.

¹³ Gordon J. Wenham, *World Biblical Commentary: Genesis 1-15*, Waco: Word Books, 1987, p. 38.

Man, created in the image of God, must never be made into an object of scientific research; that would be to damage his honor and degrade his origin. Such a graven image would cause—and has caused—a radical loss of respect and love and inevitable leads to oppression, torture, and killing.¹⁴

Thus, the worth of human beings should not be extrinsic, based on what they produce, but intrinsic because they are created in the image of God. Nothing can change this fact. I think of the quadriplegic or severely mentally retarded individual. Economics would say that he or she is only worth what he or she can produce, which may not be much according to a human production system, but the Bible and Christian ethics says that each person has immense worth, or as Brueggemann puts it, an “inalienable identity,” because he or she is created in the image of God.¹⁵ How does this assumption of the worth of every human being affect economics? If economics is defined as the method of allocating scarce resources, this conviction that all human beings have an intrinsic worth has immense implications for how we then distribute resources among ourselves.

Concerning the issue of unskilled migrant workers, thus, the challenge of Christian ethics to economics points to the problem highlighted by the Federation of Asian Bishops’ Conferences:

Whether voluntary or forced, migration reveals the vulnerability, insecurity, uncertainty, and humiliation of millions of Asians

¹⁴ Roelf L. Haan, “Man and His Methodology in Economic Science: About Abstraction and Obedience,” *Social Science in Christian Perspective*, (eds. Paul A. Marshall and Robert E. Vandervennen), Lanham: Univ. Press of America, 1988, p. 219.

¹⁵ Walter Brueggemann, *Genesis: Interpretation: A Biblical Commentary for Teaching and Preaching*. Louisville: John Knox Press, 2010, p. 31.

who find themselves on the move, either internally or beyond their national borders, as they deal with survival, uprootedness, and exploitation in their quest for a better life for themselves and their families.¹⁶

THE PROBLEM OF INDIVIDUALIZING HUMAN BEING

Another anthropological assumption of economics is an extreme individualism. To begin to understand this presupposition, we probably need to go back to what many claim is the “germinal book of modern economics,” Adam Smith’s *The Wealth of Nations* (1776).¹⁷ An excerpt from Smith’s book reads as follows:

Every individual endeavors to employ his capital so that its produce may be of greatest value. He generally neither intends to promote the public interest, nor knows how much he is promoting it. He intends his own security, only his own gain. And he is led by an invisible hand to promote an end which was no part of his intention. By pursuing his own interests he frequently promotes that of society more effectually than when he really intends to promote it.¹⁸

What Smith identifies, economics has made into a doctrine named the “invisible hand.” Samuelson and Nordhaus say regarding the doctrine, “It says that every individual, in selfishly pursuing his or her own personal good, is led, as if by an invisible hand, to achieve

¹⁶ Jonathan Y. Tan, “Migration in Asia and Its Missiological Implications : Insights from the Migration Theology of the Federation of Asians Bishops’ Conferences (FABC). *Mission Studies*, 29 (2012), p.58 (45-61)

¹⁷ Paul A. Samuelson and Richard D. Nordhaus, *Economics* (19th Edition). NY: McGraw Hill, 2009, p. 46.

¹⁸ Adam Smith, *The Wealth of Nations* (1776), as quoted in Samuelson and Nordhaus, p. 41.

the best good for all.”¹⁹ What I believe economists have done through this doctrine, is effectively enshrine individualism and selfish gain as promoting the best good for all. Empirically, I believe that we have to admit that the argument does have some credence in the modern economic life. How do all the millions of goods and services move so efficiently in and out of world’s major cities everyday? Economists would point to the invisible hand that yields the efficient result. However, on the subject of individualism Daly and Cobb tell us:

Modern economic theory originated and developed in the context of Calvinism. Both were bids for personal freedom against the interference of earthly authority. They based their bids on the conviction that beyond a very narrow sphere, motives of self-interest are overwhelmingly dominant. Economic theory differed from Calvinism only in celebrating as rational what Calvinists confessed as sinful.²⁰

The result of the “invisible hand” and the economic ethos that has developed among achievement-oriented society is an extreme individualism. Daly and Cobb move to say: “There can be no doubt that the economic theory built on this anthropology has encouraged less inhibited quest for personal gain in the business world.”²¹ This does not mean that there was no individualism before economics, but the discipline has effectively justified and sacralized individualism as the way to promote the best good for everyone involved. Economists are quick to point out that the “invisible hand” does not function correctly in all markets. Such an instance is termed a “market failure,” because the market left to its own devices

¹⁹ Samuelson and Nordhaus, p. 46.

²⁰ Daly and Cobb, p. 6.

²¹ *Ibid.*, p. 89.

will not produce the efficient result. A cost that is not accounted for by the market, and any ethical solution to a market failure, such as a law, are considered external to the economic model, and are thus termed “externalities.” Thus, the discipline of economics has separated itself from communal and ethical considerations not accounted for by the market. With the twin terms of the “invisible hand” and the “externality,” the discipline of economics presupposes and promotes an extreme individualism.

In looking at other social sciences, such as sociology, we can see that they have serious problems with this notion of extreme individualism. Back in 1840, Alex de Tocqueville, a Frenchman observing American life in the states, wrote *Democracy in America*. In the book, he “suggested that democratic societies bred individualists and warned against the morally corrosive potential of individualistic patterns of thought.”²² Sociologists have made distinctions among different types of individualism. The kind of individualism bred by aggressive materialistic pursuits is termed utilitarian individualism. A utilitarian individualist views life in largely economic terms, and “as the individual pursuit of power in a world of threatening competitors.”²³ Tocqueville’s warnings, which went largely unheeded in his day, have come to fruition in our time. As Robert N. Bellah and his colleagues poignantly pointed out in their continuation of Tocqueville’s work, *Habits of the Heart*: “Few have found a life devoted to ‘personal ambition and consumerism’ satisfactory, and most are seeking in one way or another to transcend the limitations of a self-centered life.”²⁴

²² Donald L. Gelpi, S.J. (ed.), *Beyond Individualism: Toward a Retrieval of Moral Discourse in America*, Notre Dame: Univ of Notre Dame Press, 1989, p. vii.

²³ *Ibid.*, p. 1-2.

²⁴ Robert N. Bellah, et al., *Habits of the Heart: Individualism and Commitment in*

Wealth, status, and income, were supposed to bring freedom, but instead they have brought us a society of “internal incoherence.”²⁵ Repeatedly, Bellah and his colleagues assert that a society of radical individualists is unsustainable. It yields a life without meaning, and “some of our deepest problems both as individuals and as a society are also closely linked to our individualism.”²⁶

A biblical anthropology assumes that human beings are created not only as individuals but also as communal creatures. If we look in the above verse, Genesis 1:27, we can see that humankind is referred to in both singular and plural terms. Brueggemann tells us:

This peculiar formula makes an important affirmation. On the one hand, humankind is a single entity. All person stand in solidarity before God. But on the other hand, humankind is a community, male and female. And none is in the full image of God alone. Only in community of humankind is God reflected. God is, according to this bold affirmation, not mirrored as an individual but as a community.²⁷

Thus, although men and women stand as individuals, they also stand in community where the image of God is reflected. We are incomplete without the other, and we are created such that we need the other in community. I would also pull from another verse in the first creation account: “Then God said, ‘Let **us** make humankind in **our** image, according to **our** likeness. . . .’” (Genesis 1:26, emphasis mine). Notice that God is not alone, but the pronouns referring to God, which I have emphasized, are plural. Exactly to whom the

American Life, California: Univ of California Press, 1985, p. 290.

²⁵ Ibid., p. 284.

²⁶ Ibid., p. 142.

²⁷ Ibid., p. 34.

plural pronoun refers, other than God, is somewhat uncertain.²⁸ God though, is in what we would most likely call a community. Since we are made in God's image, one of the elements of that image is probably that God made us to be in community. Another place we see that God created us to be in community is in a section of the second creation story, Genesis 2:18-25. I want to highlight certain aspects. First, God notices something that is not good out of all of God's creation: "Then the LORD God said, 'It is not good that the man should be alone; I will make him a helper as his partner'" (Genesis 2:18). For the first time God declares something in God's creation not good, which Wenham claims is a startling departure from the sevenfold refrain of God declaring God's creation good or very good in the first creation account.²⁹ Wenham also says, "It alerts the reader to the importance of companionship for man."³⁰ God creates all the animals, and brings them to Adam to name, but none of them is found to be a suitable helper for Adam. God's solution is to bring a new creation into the picture in Eve, which both Adam and God find to be a suitable partner for man. It is not good that a single human being should be alone, so God created others, and put us in community. Thus, we see again that we are created as communal creatures. I believe from this, we can conclude that, in contrast to the individualism of economics, Christian ethics holds the anthropological presupposition that human beings are created to be in community. As we saw above, this anthropological assumption is also validated by other social sciences.

²⁸ Wenham, p. 27-28.

²⁹ Ibid., p. 68.

³⁰ Ibid.

Unlike migrant professionals, most unskilled migrant workers are uprooted from their rural communal life to live in a totally different context which is more urban and thus less communal. Even when their workplace is a part of a local community, they are not introduced to, and therefore never be able to be part of, that community which normally applies different standard of living, speaks a different language, live out different cultural tradition, and employs different lifestyle. Unskilled migrant workers suffer from what Amstutz³¹ names “reduced solidarity” which is basically the lost of most supporting social and psychological factors available in a community. From the Christian ethical perspective, such an alienation from the communal dimension of life is a serious humanitarian problem which economics is unable to dealt with, and, therefore, becomes the task of the policy maker as well as civil society groups including the church.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Unskilled migrant workers are among those benefited by today’s trans-national employment market. Most of them are paid higher than the income rate normally available for them in their home countries. For the sending countries including Indonesia and the Philippines, unskilled migrant workers contribute significantly to the national income through their regular remittance. Despite such economic advantages, a number of them experience treatments which are ethically problematic.

A Christian ethical critique on this matter should appreciate the economic opportunity made available for the unskilled. However,

³¹ Mark R. Amstutz, “Two Theories of Immigration,” *First Things*, Dec 2015, p. 38

from the point of view of Christian ethics, a merely economic calculation for valuing human being is not enough and even potentially sinful. In term of unskilled migrant workers in today's economy, at least two factors should be taken into consideration: the concept of human worth and the communal nature of human being.

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